

M.Sc. Qiu Lu, Dr.-Ing. Daniel Bernhardt, M.Sc. Yushuo Wang, Prof. Dr.-Ing Michael Beckmann

Chair of Energy Process Engineering, Dresden University of Technology

Oxyfuel process for CO₂ capture in waste incineration – effects on the operation of waste incineration

TOTeM 52 – Oxy-fuel combustion and CCUS

27 – 28 May 2026 – Essen, Germany

1. Background and Motivation

Background and Motivation

BEHG: Since January 1, 2024, CO₂ emissions from thermal waste treatment have been included in the carbon pricing system

Approaches for CO₂ capture:

Pre-Combustion: Gasification with air, CO shift, CO₂ capture, combustion

Post-Combustion: Combustion with air, flue gas cleaning, CO₂ capture

Oxyfuel-Combustion: Combustion with O₂, flue gas cleaning, flue gas recirculation, CO₂ capture

Key process engineering impacts

2. Methodology

Modeling of the Oxyfuel Process

Modeling of the oxyfuel process (grate firing)

Concept 1: Wet raw flue gas recirculation upstream of flue gas treatment

Concept 2: Wet clean flue gas recirculation downstream of flue gas treatment

Concept 3: Dry clean flue gas recirculation downstream of the condenser

Specific energy consumption of the O₂ Supply

Air Separation Unit (ASU)

95 Vol.-% 240 kWh/t

99 Vol.-% 350 kWh/t

Electrolysis

99,6 Vol.-%

9 - 15 kWh/m³ i.N. O₂

Specific energy consumption of the CPU

No purification

- Flue gas only dried (dehydration)
- $\psi_{\text{CO}_2} = \psi_{\text{CO}_2_{\text{rawgas_dry}}}$

Cold box

- Dehydration
- Liquefaction at approx. 30 bar
- $\psi_{\text{CO}_2} \approx 95 \text{ Vol.-%}$

Cold box and distillation

- Dehydration
- Liquefaction at approx. 30 bar
- Distillation
- $\psi_{\text{CO}_2} \approx 99 \text{ Vol.-%}$

The effect of flue gas CO₂ content and purification method on CPU power consumption
[Rajeev Prabhakar, 2009]

3. Results of the Oxyfuel Modeling (Grate System)

Concept Overview

\dot{m}_{MSW}	23.240 kg/h	O ₂ purity	99 Vol.-%
h_u	11.170 kJ/kg	$\psi_{O_2, RG}$	20,63 Vol.-%
Air leakage	0 %	$\psi_{O_2, FG, dry}$	8 Vol.-%

		Base air mode	Oxyfuel		
			Wet raw	Wet clean	Dry clean
Grate	\dot{V}_{FG}	129805 Nm ³ /h	104349 Nm ³ /h	101830 Nm ³ /h	128347 Nm ³ /h
	$\vartheta_{theoretical}$	1245 °C	1327 °C	1328 °C	1014 °C
	ψ_{CO_2}	9.4 vol.-%	38.0 vol.-%	33.2 vol.-%	74.2 vol.-%
	ψ_{H_2O}	15.4 vol.-%	57.7 vol.-%	63.0 vol.-%	17.3 vol.-%
	ψ_{SO_2}	462 mg/Nm ³	1873 mg/Nm ³	600 mg/Nm ³	480 mg/Nm ³
Boiler	\dot{m}_{steam}	73013 kg/h	81434 kg/h	78590 kg/h	75099 kg/h
Flue gas recirculation	ψ_{O_2}	-	3.4 vol.-%	2.8 vol.-%	7.7 vol.-%
	$\dot{V}_{Recirculation}$	-	72641 Nm ³ /h (69 %)	70124 Nm ³ /h (64 %)	96641 Nm ³ /h (87 %)
	$\vartheta_{Recirculation}$	-	240 °C	168 °C	138 °C
Flue gas to CPU	$\dot{V}_{FG, CPU}$	-	14134 Nm ³ /h	14132 Nm ³ /h	14132 Nm ³ /h
	ψ_{CO_2}	-	86 vol.-%	86 vol.-%	86 vol.-%

Volumetric flow rate under standard conditions

Effect of seasonal variations

Evap.	enabled	O ₂ purity	99 Vol.-%
Season	Summer vs. Winter	$\psi_{O_2_{RG}}$	20,63 Vol.-%
Air leakage	0 %	$\psi_{O_2_{FG_{dry}}}$	8 Vol.-%

Summer

Winter

$\eta_{net,el}$

18,4 %

4,7 %

3,9 %

2,6 %

$\eta_{net,el}$

16,6 %

2,8 %

1,9 %

0,7 %

0.65 MW district heating for one line

8.35 MW district heating for one line

Einflussfaktor - O₂ Bereitstellung

Evap. enabled		ASU vs. Elektrolyse	
Season Summer		$\psi_{O_2_RG}$	20,63 Vol.-%
Air leakage 0 %		$\psi_{O_2_FG_dry}$	8 Vol.-%

ASU O₂ 99 Vol.-%

$\eta_{Netto,el}$

18,4 %

4,7 %

3,9 %

2,6 %

Electrolysis O₂ 99,6 Vol.-%

$\eta_{Netto,el}$

18,4 %

15,8 %

15,0 %

13,7 %

Electrolysis: 144 - 239 MW

Effect of O₂ purity

Evap.	enabled	O₂ purity	99 Vol.-% vs. 95 Vol.-%
Season	Summer	$\psi_{O_2_{RG}}$	20,63 Vol.-%
Air leakage	0 %	$\psi_{O_2_{FG_{dry}}}$	8 Vol.-%

O₂ purity 99%

$\eta_{net,el}$ **18,4 %** **4,7 %** **3,9 %** **2,6 %**

O₂ purity 95%

$\eta_{net,el}$ **18,4 %** **7,5 %** **6,7 %** **5,5 %**

Effect of air leakage

Flue gas recirculation	Wet clean	O ₂ purity	95 Vol.-%
Air leakage	0 % - 9 %	$\psi_{O_2_FG_dry}$	8 Vol.-%

Effect of air leakage

Evap.	enabled	O ₂ purity	95 Vol.-%
Season	Summer	$\psi_{O_2_{RG}}$	20,63 Vol.-%
Air leakage	0 % vs. 3 %	$\psi_{O_2_{FG_{dry}}}$	8 Vol.-%

0 % Air leakage

$\eta_{net,el}$

18,4 %

7,5 %

6,7 %

5,5 %

3 % Air leakage

$\eta_{net,el}$

18,4 %

6,9 %

6,2 %

5,0 %

Effect of excess oxygen

Evap.	enabled	O ₂ purity	95 Vol.-%
Season	Summer	$\psi_{O_2_RG}$	20,63 Vol.-%
Air leakage	3 %	$\psi_{O_2_FG_dry}$	4 Vol.-% vs. 8 Vol.-%

$\psi_{O_2_FG_dry} = 8 \text{ Vol.-%}$

$\psi_{O_2_FG_dry} = 4 \text{ Vol.-%}$

$\eta_{Net,el}$

18,4 %

6,9 %

6,2 %

5,0 %

$\eta_{Net,el}$

19,7 %

7,6 %

7,1 %

6,4 %

$\psi_{O_2_FG_dry} 8 \text{ Vol.-%} \rightarrow 4 \text{ Vol.-%}$, smaller flue gas volume flow \rightarrow lower losses in the flue gas path
Reduced effort in ASU and CPU

4. Conclusions

Conclusions

- **Three oxyfuel concepts:** (1) wet raw, (2) wet clean, (3) dry clean
 - wet raw: 4–5 times higher SO₂ and HCl, not feasible
 - wet clean: most suitable option
 - dry clean: feasible, lower thermal efficiency
- **Influencing parameters**
 - Season: +8 MW district heating vs. -1.4 MW_e electrical power ($\eta_{e1} = \pm 2\%$)
 - Electrolysis: Future Scenarios ($\eta_{e1} = +11\%$)
 - O₂ purity: 99% and 95% (optimal), ($\eta_{e1} = +2.8\%$)
 - Air leakage: large reduction in CO₂ concentration, 3% Air leakage ($\eta_{e1} = -0.5\%$)
 - O₂ excess: 8% → 4%, lower heat losses, less effort in ASU and CPU, higher efficiency ($\eta_{e1} = +0.7 - 1.4\%$)
 - Grate system: air combustion 13.3 MW_e ($\eta_{e1} = 18.4\%$) vs. oxyfuel 3.6–5.0 MW_e ($\eta_{e1} \approx 5.0-6.9\%$)

Thank you for your interest!

Fakultät Maschinenwesen

Institut für Verfahrens- und Umwelttechnik
Professur für Energieverfahrenstechnik

M.Sc. Qiu Lu

Telefon: +49 351-463-39503

0351-463-33143

E-Mail: qiu.lu@tu-dresden.de

Web: www.energieverfahrenstechnik.de

GMVA Oberhausen

Gemeinschafts-Müll-Verbrennungsanlage Niederrhein

Liricher Straße 121

46049 Oberhausen

Deutschland

Telefon: +49 208 8594-0

Fax: +49 208 8594-210

Web: info@gmva.de